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Non Convergence of Cubic Spline Interpolation of Continuous Functions

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Karun Lata Shukla

Assistant Professor
Department Of
Mathematics
R C C V Girls Degree
College
Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

There have been studies on such functions whose interpolating splines do not converge to the functions of interpolation.

Keywords Interpolation, Convergence And Continuity.

Introduction

Let $\pi_n : 0 = x_0 < x_1, \dots < x_n = 1$ be a subdivision of $[0,1]$ and let $\pi \equiv \pi_n$

with $x_{n+k} = x_{k+1} (k = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots)$.

Objective of study

There have been studies on such functions whose interpolating splines do not converge to the functions of interpolation.

Review of Literature

Convergence of cubic spline function by Mair and Sharma [4] imposed a condition on partition points. The following was proved.

THEOREM 1.1: Let $f \in C_\pi$. where C_π denotes the class of 1-periodic continuous functions on $(-\infty, \infty)$ with $\max_i (h_i) = \delta$, $h_i = x_i - x_{i-1}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$). Suppose

$$\max_{|i-j|=1} h_i h_j^{-1} = P < \sqrt{2}.$$

Then for the interpolatory cubic splines $\sigma(x) \equiv \sigma(f; x)$, we have

$$\|f - \sigma\| \leq \left(1 + \frac{3}{4} \frac{P}{(2 - P^2)}\right) \omega(f; \delta).$$

Let f be continuous on $[0,1]$. A function s is a cubic spline interpolant associated with f and π_n if

(a) $s \in C^2[0, 1]$;

(b) $s(x)$ is a cubic polynomial on (x_{i-1}, x_i) for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$;

and

(c) $s(x_i) = f(x_i)$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, n$.

We write $s = N_n f$ for the cubic spline interpolant to f prescribed by

(a), (b), (c) and

(d₁) $s''(0) = s''(1) = 0$.

Similarly $s = S_n f$ for the cubic spline interpolant to f prescribed by (a),

(b), (c) and

(d₂) $s'(0) = s'(1) = 0$.

And

 $s = L_n f$ for the cubic spline interpolant to f prescribed by (a), (b), (c)

and

(d₃) $s'(0) = s'(1)$ and $s''(0) = s''(1)$.

Let $h_i = x_i - x_{i-1}$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and $h_0 = h_n$.

Let

$$m_n = \max\left\{\frac{h_i}{h_j} : |i - j| = 1 \text{ and } i, j = 0, 1, \dots, n\right\}.$$

We have the following theorem due to Martin [2] for non convergence.

Analysis**THEOREM 1.2:** For each fixed $m > \frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}$ there exists a sequence $\{\pi_n\}$ for which $m_n \leq m$ for all n while

$$\limsup \|N_n\| = \limsup \|S_n\| = \limsup \|L_n\| = \infty.$$

Result and Discussion

In this paper, we will make a detailed study of a non-convergence of spline function considered by Martin [2]. We obtain the inverse matrix of the system of equations for computation of the spline function for each interval. At each point of the mid of subinterval, from the proof, it can be seen that in the neighbouring subintervals of the partition is also non-convergent. The constant in the lower bound of the estimate is improved.

We consider the partition of $[0, 1]$ be as follows:

Let $n = 2k + 1$, $k = 1, 2, \dots$. We consider h defined by the equation

$$2h + 2mh + \dots + m^k h = 1;$$

and let the division of the interval $[0,1]$ be as follows:

$$(2.1) \quad [0 \text{-----} | \text{---} m^{k-1}h \text{---} | \text{---} m^k h \text{---} | \text{---} m^{k-1}h \text{---} | \text{-----} 1],$$

that is $h_{i+1} = h_{n-i} = m^i h$, for $i = 0, 1, \dots, k$.

THEOREM 2.1: For the partition defined in (2.1), the interpolatory spline function interpolating the continuous function $f \in [0, 1]$, $f(x_0) = 1$ and $f(x_i) = 0$; for all i . Under the boundary conditions $s''(0) = s''(1) = 0$, the spline function at any point of the middle partition tends to infinity. precisely in subinterval $[x_k, x_{k+1}]$, we have the following:

$$\begin{aligned} & s(x_k + \sigma h_{k+1}) \\ &= 3(-1)^k m^{2k} \sigma(1 - \sigma) \{ (12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} - \beta_2^{n-3}) \\ &+ \sqrt{(1 + m + m^2)}(12m^2 + 21m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} + \beta_2^{n-3}) \}^{-1} \\ & \{ (\beta_1^{n-k-1} - \beta_2^{n-k-1}) ((1 - \sigma)(2m + 1) + \sigma m(4m^2 + 5m + 3)) \\ &+ \sqrt{(1 + m + m^2)}(\beta_1^{n-k-1} + \beta_2^{n-k-1})(2(1 - \sigma) + \sigma m(4m + 3)) \} , \end{aligned}$$

where $0 \leq \sigma \leq 1$.

Remarks:

1. From the expression for the spline, we see that

$$|s(x_k + \sigma h_{k+1})| \geq 3 \left(\frac{m^2}{\beta_1}\right)^k \sigma(1-\sigma) \frac{2m+1+\sigma m-\sigma+4\sigma m^3+5\sigma m^2}{(12m^3+27m^2+27m+12)} \beta_1^2.$$

At $\sigma = \frac{1}{2}$, we get

$$\geq \frac{3}{4}(5.8) \left(\frac{m^2}{\beta_1}\right)^k \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } k \rightarrow \infty \text{ in the proof of the Theorem 2.1, if the}$$

partition satisfied the condition $m > \frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}$.

2. In the proof, we also obtain the expression for the spline for different intervals. It can be seen from the observation after the proof of the theorem that the bounds for the spline function of neighbouring intervals of the middle interval, tends to infinity as the number of partitions tends to infinity.

Proof of Theorem 2.1: Let $s_{i+1}(x) = s(x)$ be spline in the interval $[x_i, x_{i+1}]$.

Assume $s'(x_i) = \mu_i$, $s(x)$ interpolates to y_0, y_1, \dots, y_n at x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n . The spline function is defined by the following:

$$s'(x) = \frac{1}{h_{i+1}^2} [(2x_i + x_{i+1} - 3x)(x_{i+1} - x)\mu_i - (x - x_i)(2x_{i+1} + x_i - 3x)\mu_{i+1}]$$

$$+\frac{1}{h_{i+1}^3}6(x_{i+1} - x)(x - x_i)(y_{i+1} - y_i) \text{ for } i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

Whence

$$(2.2) \quad s(x) = \frac{1}{h_{i+1}^2}[(x - x_i)(x_{i+1} - x)^2\mu_i - (x - x_i)^2(x_{i+1} - x)\mu_{i+1}] \\ + \frac{1}{h_{i+1}^3}[y_i(2x - 2x_i + h_{i+1})(x_{i+1} - x)^2 \\ + y_{i+1}(-2x + 2x_{i+1} + h_{i+1})(x - x_i)^2].$$

Set $y_0 = 1$ and $y_i = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Hence for a point σh_{t+1} , $0 \leq \sigma \leq 1$, $0 \leq t \leq n$ in $[x_t, x_{t+1}]$, we have

$$s(\sigma h_1) = \sigma(1 - \sigma)h_1((1 - \sigma)\mu_0 - \sigma\mu_1) + (1 + 2\sigma)(1 - \sigma)^2, \text{ for } t = 0;$$

$$(2.3a) \quad s(x_t + \sigma h_{t+1}) = m^t \sigma(1 - \sigma)((1 - \sigma)\mu_t - \sigma\mu_{t+1})h;$$

for $t = 1, 2, \dots, k - 1$;

$$(2.3b) \quad s(x_k + \sigma h_{k+1}) = m^k \sigma(1 - \sigma)((1 - \sigma)\mu_k - \sigma\mu_{k+1})h;$$

for $t = k$, and

$$(2.3c) \quad s(x_t + \sigma h_{t+1}) = m^{2k-t} \sigma(1 - \sigma)((1 - \sigma)\mu_t - \sigma\mu_{t+1})h;$$

for $t = k + 1, k + 2, \dots, n - 1$.

Now we proceed to find out the values of $\mu_t s$. To impose the continuity

of $s''(x)$, we consider

$$s''(x) = -\frac{1}{h_{i+1}^2}[2(2x_{i+1} + x_i - 3x)\mu_i + 2(2x_i + x_{i+1} - 3x)\mu_{i+1}] \\ + \frac{1}{h_{i+1}^3}6(x_i + x_{i+1} - 2x)(y_{i+1} - y_i).$$

Continuity requirement of $s''(x)$ at x_i gives

$$(2.4) \quad m\mu_i + 2(1 + m)\mu_{i+1} + \mu_{i+2} = 3\frac{1}{h_{i+2}}(y_{i+2} - y_{i+1}) + 3m\frac{1}{h_{i+1}}(y_{i+1} - y_i); \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n-2.$$

Using the boundary conditions $s''(0) = s''(1) = 0$, we obtain

$$(2.5) \quad 2\mu_0 + \mu_1 = \frac{-3}{h},$$

and

$$(2.6) \quad \mu_{n-1} + 2\mu_n = 0.$$

The coefficient matrix of the above system of equations for $n \geq 3$ is

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ m & 2(1+m) & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m & 2(1+m) & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & m & 2(1+m) & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & m & \frac{3}{2} + 2m \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mu_0 \\ \mu_1 \\ \mu_2 \\ \dots \\ \dots \\ \dots \\ \mu_{n-1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-3}{h} \\ \frac{-3m}{h} \\ 0 \\ \dots \\ \dots \\ \dots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We write the above equation as

$$(2.7) \quad c^1 D = C.$$

We use the notation that $|A|$ denotes the determinant of the matrix

A.

LEMMA 2.1: If inverse of c^1 is $(\hat{a}_{ij}) = \hat{A}$, then

$$\hat{a}_{ij} = \frac{1}{|c_n^1|} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (-m)^{i-j} (|c_{n-i}| - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-i-1}|) |c_{j-1}^1|; \quad i \geq j, \quad 3 \geq j \geq 1, \\ (-m)^{i-j} (|c_{n-i}| - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-i-1}|) ((\frac{1}{2})^{j-3} |c_2^1| \\ + \sum_{l=3}^{j-1} (\frac{1}{2})^{j-l-1} |c_l^1|); \quad i \geq j > 3, \\ (-1)^{j-i} (|c_{n-j}| - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-j-1}|) |c_{i-1}^1|; \quad j \geq i, \quad 3 \geq i \geq 1, \\ (-1)^{j-i} (|c_{n-j}| - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-j-1}|) ((\frac{1}{2})^{i-3} |c_2^1| \\ + \sum_{l=3}^{i-1} (\frac{1}{2})^{i-l-1} |c_l^1|); \quad j \geq i > 3. \end{array} \right.$$

Proof of Lemma 2.1: Obviously the matrix c^1 is diagonally dominant and so it is non singular. In the proof of the lemma we need the following matrix

$$c = \begin{bmatrix} 2(1+m) & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ m & 2(1+m) & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m & 2(1+m) & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m & 2(1+m) & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & m & 2(1+m) & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & m & 2(1+m) \end{bmatrix}$$

We write $|c_{-1}| = 0, |c_0| = 1, |c_1| = 2(1+m), |c_2| = 4m^2 + 7m + 4$. It

can be seen [1] that

$$|c_n| = \frac{\beta_1^{n+1} - \beta_2^{n+1}}{\beta_1 - \beta_2}, \text{ where}$$

$$\beta_1 = m + 1 + \sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}$$

and

$$\beta_2 = m + 1 - \sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}.$$

First we compute $|c^1|$.

We write

$$|c_{-1}^1| = 0, |c_0^1| = 1, |c_1^1| = 2, |c_2^1| = 4 + 3m.$$

We claim that for $n \geq 3$,

$$(2.8) \quad |c_n^1| = (3 + 4m) |c_{n-2}| - \left(\frac{7}{2} + 2m\right)m |c_{n-3}| + m^2 |c_{n-4}|$$

$$= \frac{1}{4\sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}} [(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} - \beta_2^{n-3})$$

$$+ \sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}(12m^2 + 21m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} + \beta_2^{n-3})].$$

We prove this by induction. Obviously

$$|c_3^1| = (3 + 4m) |c_1| - \left(\frac{7}{2} + 2m\right)m |c_0| + m^2 |c_{-1}|.$$

Assume it holds for any $n > 3$. We have

$$|c_{n+1}^1| = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ m & 2(1+m) & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m & 2(1+m) & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m & 2(1+m) & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 2(1+m) & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & m & \frac{3}{2} + 2m \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \frac{1}{4\sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}} [(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-2} - \beta_2^{n-2}) + \sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}(12m^2 + 21m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-2} + \beta_2^{n-2})].$$

We consider $B = c^1 \hat{A} = (a_{ij})(\hat{a}_{ij}) = (b_{ij})$, say.

We have

$$b_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n a_{i k} \hat{a}_{k j}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

To prove the lemma it is sufficient to show that B is the identity matrix.

We see that for diagonal elements

$$|c_n^1| b_{ii} = |c_n^1|, \quad \text{for all } i,$$

where

$$|c_n^1| b_{ii} = \begin{cases} \sum_{k=1}^n a_{i k} \hat{a}_{k i}; & i = 1 \\ (|c_{n-i} - \frac{1}{2}| c_{n-i-1}|)(-m |c_{i-2}^1| + 2(1+m) |c_{i-1}^1|) \\ + (-m)(|c_{n-i-1} - \frac{1}{2}| c_{n-i-2}|) |c_{i-1}^1|; & 2 \leq i \leq 3, \\ (|c_{n-i} - \frac{1}{2}| c_{n-i-1}|)(-m \sum_{l=2}^{i-2} (\frac{1}{2})^{i-l-2} |c_l^1|) \\ + 2(1+m) \sum_{l=2}^{i-1} (\frac{1}{2})^{i-l-1} |c_l^1| \\ + (-m)(|c_{n-i-1} - \frac{1}{2}| c_{n-i-2}|) \sum_{l=2}^{i-1} (\frac{1}{2})^{i-l-1} |c_l^1|; & 4 \leq i \leq n-1, \\ (-m) \sum_{l=2}^{i-2} (\frac{1}{2})^{i-l-2} |c_l^1| + (\frac{3}{2} + 2m) \sum_{l=2}^{i-1} (\frac{1}{2})^{i-l-1} |c_l^1|; & i = n. \end{cases}$$

And for non diagonal elements, we have to show that

$$|c_n^1| b_{ij} = 0, \quad \text{for all } i \text{ and } j,$$

where

$$|c_n^1| b_{ij} = \begin{cases} (|c_{n-j} | - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-j-1} |)(-1)^{j-2}(-2 |c_0^1 | + |c_1^1 |); & 1=i < j \leq n, \\ m(|c_{n-i+1} | - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-i} |) + 2(1+m)(-m)(|c_{n-i} | - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-i-1} |) \\ + m^2(|c_{n-i-1} | - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-i-2} |); & 1 = j < i \leq n, \\ m(-m)^{n-j-1}(|c_1 | - \frac{1}{2} |c_0 |) \\ + (\frac{3}{2} + 2m)(-m)^{n-j}(|c_0 | - \frac{1}{2} |c_{-1} |); & i > j, j = 2 \text{ and } 3, \\ \sum_{l=2}^{j-1} (\frac{1}{2})^{j-l-1} |c_l^1 | m(-m)^{n-j-1}(|c_1 | - \frac{1}{2} |c_0 |) \\ + (\frac{3}{2} + 2m)(-m)^{n-j}(|c_0 | - \frac{1}{2} |c_{-1} |); & i > j > 3, \\ (|c_{n-i-1} | - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-i-2} |)(m(-1)^j |c_{i-2}^1 | \\ + 2(1+m)(-1)^{i-1} |c_{i-1}^1 | + (-1)^{i-2} \sum_{l=2}^i (\frac{1}{2})^{i-l} |c_l^1 |); & i < j \leq n, 2 \leq i \leq 3, \\ (|c_{n-i-1} | - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-i-2} |)(-1)^i [m \sum_{l=2}^{i-2} (\frac{1}{2})^{i-2-l} |c_l^1 | \\ - 2(1+m) \sum_{l=2}^{i-1} (\frac{1}{2})^{i-l-1} |c_l^1 | + \sum_{l=2}^i (\frac{1}{2})^{i-l} |c_l^1 |]; & 3 < i < j \leq n. \end{cases}$$

Thus

$$b_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{for } i = j \\ 0; & \text{for } i \neq j \end{cases} .$$

This completes the proof of the Lemma.

Now we compute μ_i s. By the relation (2.7), we get $D = (c^1)^{-1}C$.

This gives

$$\mu_0 = \frac{-3 |c_{n-1}| + |c_{n-2}|}{2h |c_n^1|},$$

and

$$\mu_t = \frac{3}{h}(-m)^t \frac{|c_{n-t-1}| - \frac{1}{2} |c_{n-t-2}|}{|c_n^1|}, \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, n-1.$$

Immediately from (2.6) we find

$$\mu_n = -\frac{3}{2h}(-m)^{n-1} \frac{1}{|c_n^1|}.$$

Using the above computed values of μ_t s in equation (2.3a), we get for

$$1 \leq t \leq k-1,$$

$$\begin{aligned} (2.9) \quad & |s(x_t + \sigma h_{t+1})| \\ &= 3m^{2t} \sigma(1-\sigma) \times \\ & \{(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} - \beta_2^{n-3}) \\ & + \sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}(12m^2 + 21m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} + \beta_2^{n-3})\}^{-1} \\ & \{(\beta_1^{n-t-1} - \beta_2^{n-t-1})((1-\sigma)(2m+1) + \sigma m(4m^2 + 5m + 3)) \\ & + \sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}(\beta_1^{n-t-1} + \beta_2^{n-t-1})(2(1-\sigma) + \sigma m(4m+3))\}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly from (2.3b) and (2.3c), we see that

$$\begin{aligned} (2.10) \quad & |s(x_k + \sigma h_{k+1})| \\ &= 3m^{2k} \sigma(1-\sigma) \times \\ & \{(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} - \beta_2^{n-3}) \\ & + \sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}(12m^2 + 21m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} + \beta_2^{n-3})\}^{-1} \\ & \{(\beta_1^{n-k-1} - \beta_2^{n-k-1})((1-\sigma)(2m+1) + \sigma m(4m^2 + 5m + 3)) \\ & + \sqrt{(1+m+m^2)}(\beta_1^{n-k-1} + \beta_2^{n-k-1})(2(1-\sigma) + \sigma m(4m+3))\}; \end{aligned}$$

and for $k + 1 \leq t \leq n - 1$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.11) \quad & |s(x_t + \sigma h_{t+1})| \\
 &= 3m^{2k}\sigma(1 - \sigma)\{(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} - \beta_2^{n-3}) \\
 &+ \sqrt{(1 + m + m^2)}(12m^2 + 21m + 12)(\beta_1^{n-3} + \beta_2^{n-3})\}^{-1} \\
 &[(\beta_1^{n-t-1} - \beta_2^{n-t-1})((1 - \sigma)(2m + 1) + \sigma m(4m^2 + 5m + 3)) \\
 &+ \sqrt{(1 + m + m^2)}(\beta_1^{n-t-1} + \beta_2^{n-t-1})(2(1 - \sigma) + \sigma m(4m + 3))].
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the theorem.

We observe that

$$(1 - \sigma)(2m + 1) + \sigma m(4m^2 + 5m + 3) \leq \sqrt{(1 + m + m^2)}(2(1 - \sigma) + \sigma m(4m + 3)),$$

and

$$(\sqrt{(1 + m + m^2)}(12m^2 + 21m + 12) < (12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12).$$

Equation (2.9) gives for $1 \leq t \leq k - 1$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |s(x_t + \sigma h_{t+1})| \\
 & \geq 3m^{2t}\sigma(1 - \sigma) \frac{((1 - \sigma)(2m + 1) + \sigma m(4m^2 + 5m + 3))}{(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)} \frac{\beta_1^{2k-t}}{\beta_1^{2(k-1)}} \\
 & = 3 \left(\frac{m^2}{\beta_1}\right)^t \sigma(1 - \sigma) \frac{2m + 1 + \sigma m - \sigma + 4\sigma m^3 + 5\sigma m^2}{(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)} \beta_1^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly (2.10) yields,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |s(x_k + \sigma h_{k+1})| \\
 & \geq 3 m^{2k}\sigma(1 - \sigma) \frac{((1 - \sigma)(2m + 1) + \sigma m(4m^2 + 5m + 3))}{(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)} \frac{\beta_1^k}{\beta_1^{2(k-1)}} \\
 & = 3 \left(\frac{m^2}{\beta_1}\right)^k \sigma(1 - \sigma) \frac{2m + 1 + \sigma m - \sigma + 4\sigma m^3 + 5\sigma m^2}{(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)} \beta_1^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Again (2.11) gives for $k + 1 \leq t \leq n - 1$,

Conclusion

$$\begin{aligned}
& |s(x_t + \sigma h_{t+1})| \\
& \geq 3m^{2k}\sigma(1-\sigma) \frac{((1-\sigma)(2m+1) + \sigma m(4m^2 + 5m + 3)) \beta_1^{2k-t}}{(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12) \beta_1^{2(k-1)}} \\
& = 3 \left(\frac{m^{2k}}{\beta_1^t}\right) \sigma(1-\sigma) \frac{2m+1 + \sigma m - \sigma + 4\sigma m^3 + 5\sigma m^2}{(12m^3 + 27m^2 + 27m + 12)} \beta_1^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Here $m^2 - \beta_1 > 0$ for $m > \frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}$.

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